

ARCHITECTURE EVALUATION THROUGH THE USE OF SIMULATION ENVIRONMENT BENCHMARKING

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ABSTRACT

The changing Navy needs of future aircraft combined with a decline in the Department of Defense budget has increased the need for the employment of open system architectures that can be readily upgraded as technology evolves. It therefore becomes necessary to evaluate how new technology fits into the framework of an open architecture system. A methodology for architecture assessment has been developed and is currently being used by the Advanced Avionics Subsystems and Technologies Signal Processor Evaluation Program in order to assess the ability of a processor module to perform a particular signal processor algorithm.

THE CHANGING NAVY NEED

The new world order combined with a decline in the Department of Defense budget has caused the Navy to change its stand on Naval Aviation for the future. The changing World situations have prompted the need for additional mission modes whereas the declining budget has resulted in the need to increase the deployment lifetime of an aircraft to twenty-five years. This shift increases the need for open systems architectures which can be readily upgraded as technology evolves. The need to evaluate how emerging technology fits within the framework of an open architecture leads directly to simulation.

THE OPEN ARCHITECTURE APPROACH TO MISSION COMPUTING

One of the areas affected by the need for the employment of advanced technology is the mission computer. Past Naval Aircraft mission

computers have been designed using a Federated Architecture approach. In a Federated Architecture, avionics subsystems are developed to support a specific requirement, usually in a "black box" fashion. These subsystems are generally developed using Government funds and equipment upgrades usually end up being sole source. The hardware reusability of a Federated System is limited and in most cases the addition of a capability or new technology requires a redesign of the existing system. Not only is the development of such systems expensive but also is the life cycle support of the Federated Systems. The Federated Architecture approach does not lend itself to sharing among aircraft platforms, the reuse of developed software, or support of upgrades and technology insertions. A lack in these capabilities drives up both the supportability costs and the retrofit costs thus making the system very expensive over an extended aircraft life cycle.

With the decreasing defense dollars and the advent of new technology, the Government, and hence the Navy, has steered away from the Federated Architecture approach and has moved toward the Integrated Open Architecture approach for mission computers. Programs such as the Joint Integrated Avionics Working Group (JIAWG) and the Navy's Next Generation Computer Resources (NGCR) have moved the Navy forward in the development and future deployment of integrated open architecture mission computers. In an open architecture the subsystems are developed as modules that are integrated into a common, open mission computer system. The modules can be both general or special purpose in nature and are developed with common interfaces so that they can be integrated along a common backplane. The advantage of this type of architecture is that it is designed with

open, non-proprietary interfaces so that any vendor may build a module to be integrated into the system, thus increasing both the selection and competition among vendors. This type of system lends itself to a Contractor Furnished Equipment (CFE) or Commercial Off-The-Shelf (COTS) purchasing structure thus increasing the affordability and buying power of the Navy. Now, instead of being forced to go out and develop systems under sole source type agreements it is possible to buy systems that are comprised of processor modules from competing vendors which greatly improves the overall affordability of the system. An open architecture lends itself to reuse and sharing among platforms, the goal of both the JIAWG and NCR programs, and thus allows for the ease of upgrades and support for the planned extended deployment life of Naval Aircraft.

ASSESSMENT OF OPEN ARCHITECTURES

With the move toward open system architectures comes an opportunity for the Navy to assess the performability of a module as it functions within a system prior to the procurement, and even final development of the module. Given a set of platform requirements it is necessary to determine first if the requirements can be met using currently available modules or if a special purpose module needs to be developed, and second that if a number of modules exist that are advertised as meeting a specific requirement that the best module for the job is chosen. The Advanced Avionics Subsystems and Technologies (AAST) Signal Processor Evaluation Program is tasked with the job of determining the methodology for evaluating a module's applicability to a Navy processing requirement and to determine the feasibility of integrating a module into an open architecture system. Choosing a module to meet a requirement is like making a choice from a supermarket whose selection can be numerous. It was therefore necessary for the AAST Signal Processor Evaluation task to develop a methodology that could be used in order to make the task at hand a manageable one. The methodology depicted in Figure 1 is that which was chosen and is currently being put into use for the task of module architecture assessment.

The assessment methodology begins with a specific mission processing platform requirement. This requirement is defined based on mission scenarios and sensor modes of the target aircraft platform. This requirement is translated into a corresponding signal processing algorithm (developed outside of this task) and is used to determine a set of hardware module architectures that may possibly be applicable. Once the hardware module architecture and signal processing algorithm to be modeled are chosen the algorithm is mapped onto the hardware. This mapping assigns pieces of the algorithm flow to hardware resources within the architecture. As part of this mapping activity it is necessary to decide what hierarchical levels will be needed for each "piece". In order to have a high fidelity model it is necessary to instantiate down to a level of detail that provides enough information about the hardware/software system being modeled but is not so deep that simulation times become excessive. This level of detail may be based on the level of experience with similar architectures and of the module, the level of complexity of the module's architecture, and on the desired results of the simulation. The level of detail for a module is going to be directly related to the number of independently programmable processing elements. For example, a module with multiple pipelines operating in a Single Instruction Multiple Data (SIMD) manner can be modeled monolithically whereas a module with a hypercube design would require each processing element and the communication paths between each element to be modeled. The level of detail does not have to be uniform throughout a model but rather should be consistent with what makes sense based on what it is you want from the simulation.

The next step in the assessment process is to form a set of parameters. These parameters are derived from the hardware module and algorithm information. These parameters will be the crux of the methodology in that they will control the simulation, allow for trade-off analysis of various configurations, and provide for possible simulation model sharing.

The simulation environment currently being used by this task is the Architecture Design and Assessment System (ADAS) developed by Research Triangle Institute (RTI). ADAS

Figure 1: Architecture Assessment Methodology

models hardware and software using directed graphs in which nodes represent individual software operations or hardware functional elements and arcs represent data and control flow paths. The ADAS models are developed in a hierarchical fashion in which nodes can be expanded into subgraphs. These subgraphs represent a refinement of the software operation or a hardware component represented by the parent node. At the lowest level instantiation each software process within the algorithm is mapped to a specific hardware component within the architecture being modeled.

In the methodology, the Hardware Architecture and the Algorithm Data Flow are

modeled as a hierarchy of directed graphs within the ADAS environment. The simulation of these graphs is controlled by a set of attributes which are determined by the hardware and algorithm parameters. In ADAS, this set of attributes are contained in Attribute Definition Language files. Assigned attributes of the nodes and arcs control the behavior of the model. These attributes define the software to hardware mapping and timings as to when and how long a process holds a hardware resource.

During the simulation of the model, the performance of the hardware processing the algorithm function is measured. This performance is based upon the amount of time a

software process utilizes the hardware resources to which it is mapped. If more than one software process within the algorithm are mapped onto a single hardware resource then that resource is shared and must be contended for within the model simulation. In order to make the model as valid as possible it may be necessary to explicitly model how the contentions for hardware resources are handled within the actual hardware. It may also be necessary to examine the mapping of the algorithm to hardware so to minimize the contentions wherever possible.

The functioning of the model during simulation is contained in output files that are generated within the ADAS environment. The ADAS output files are used to analyze the performance of the hardware architecture being modeled as it performs a certain algorithm. From these files, hardware resource utilizations and system bottlenecks can be identified. If a hardware resource is over utilized to the point where system bottlenecks are occurring, a trade-off is made and input parameters are changed and the system is re-simulated. This loop of trade-off analysis of a particular module architecture ends when the system output utilizations are acceptable or if the module is deemed inappropriate.

Along with the trade-off analysis that is done within the simulation of a single architecture it is also necessary to trade-off alternative hardware architectures. In this type of analysis, the simulation outputs from various architecture models performing the same algorithm (with the same algorithm parameters) are compared. It may also be necessary to simulate a single architecture as it operates on a number of algorithms. Both of these cases bring up the importance of partitioning the model into hardware and software pieces that can be extracted out and modified very easily. The ideal situation would be to have a library of hardware architecture and software signal processing algorithm models. With a library of this type it would be very easy to reuse models in order to do a mix-and-match through simulation assessment of both hardware and software. Currently this type of mixing-and-matching of the models is not possible with ADAS since the hardware and software models are tied very closely together to the point where it would be very difficult to partition. It is a goal of the AAST Signal Processor Evaluation Task to

bring this concept into reality either by trying to evolve ADAS or going to some other simulation environment.

EXAMPLE MODULE ASSESSMENT

The first module assessment performed within the AAST Signal Processor Evaluation task using the described methodology was a simulation of a Synthetic Aperture RADAR (SAR) algorithm mapped onto the F-22 JIAWG architecture. The SAR algorithm used in this simulation is essentially a straight line data flow from RADAR sensor input to display output and is depicted in Figure 2. The main goal of this simulation was to determine how a single cluster within the JIAWG architecture performed the algorithm. A single cluster within the F-22 JIAWG architecture consisting of a Data Network/Global Bulk Memory (DN/GBM) and the processing elements directly ported to that DN/GBM. The model did not consider the full F-22 JIAWG architecture which would consist of multiple DN/GBM clusters.

At the start of the process it was necessary to determine which module or modules from the F-22 JIAWG Common Module Set would be best suited for performing the SAR processing task. Through an examination of the SAR algorithm it was determined that a combination of data and signal processors would be needed. From the available JIAWG module suite, it was determined that a general purpose data processor and a pipeline architecture signal processor would be best suited for the SAR application and hence the Dual Data Processor Element (DDPE) and the Dual Signal Processor Element (DSPE) were chosen for evaluation.

Following the methodology, the next effort would be to determine the level of modeling detail that would be needed. Since the SAR algorithm is straight line in nature and the SPE is a single pipeline architecture it was determined that it would not be necessary to model the details of the interaction of the pipe with operand memory because there is no resource contention for the memory. Rather, a single node representing a signal processing chain mapped onto the SPE would be sufficient. The shared port of the two SPEs on a DSPE module was

Figure 2: SAR Algorithm Data Flow

modeled since the port is a source of contention between SPEs. The algorithm was then broken down into data processing and signal processing parts, each being mapped onto the DDPE and DSPE respectfully.

A determination of the SAR algorithm and F-22 JIAWG architecture parameters was the next step that needed to be completed before the actual simulation could take place. There are two factors that need to be considered when deciding what needs to be parameterized. First, it is necessary to parameterize those variables that will need to be changed in order to perform the trade-off studies within this simulation. Second, it is also necessary to structure the parameters in such a way that other architectures can be evaluated thus reusing the existing ADAS model. These parameters are fed into the simulation by means of Attribute Definition Language (ADL) files.

Within the ADAS simulation environment, directed graph models depicting the data flow of the SAR algorithm as mapped onto the F-22 JIAWG architecture were developed. The trade-offs that were made as part of this simulation are the SAR map accuracy, SAR map display update rate, SAR map resolution, and number of processor modules available to process SAR data within a F-22 JIAWG architecture single cluster. Simulation output files were than analyzed as the final stage of the process in order to determine the F-22 JIAWG architecture hardware resource utilizations and if any bottlenecks existed within the architecture.

FUTURE DIRECTION

The future goal of the AAST Signal Processor Evaluation task is to comprise a library of signal processor benchmarks within the simulation environment with the SAR algorithm being the first. The second algorithm to be added to this benchmark library and is currently being developed within the simulation environment is the Infrared Search and Track (IRST) algorithm. Currently the IRST as it maps to existing F-22 JIAWG modules are being examined. Processor modules that are currently being developed under the Ultra-Reliable Digital Avionics (URDA) Program are also being looked at in terms of IRST algorithm performance. The third benchmark that will be added to the library will be an Electronic Warfare (EW) algorithm. EW algorithms, unlike the SAR and IRST, tend to be more data processing intensive. This will offer the opportunity to evaluate a different set of modules from the F-22 JIAWG architecture suite.

The extensiveness of the assessment methodology will also be explored as a future task. In particular, how the methodology applies to the E-2C mission computer, once one is selected, will be determined. The model developed under this effort will be a mapping of the IRST algorithm, available from the signal processor benchmark library, to the E-2C Mission Computer. This simulation will demonstrate the applicability of benchmarks to other architectures aside from the F-22 JIAWG architecture.